

AIP | The Journal of Chemical Physics

Perspective: Chemical reactions in ionic liquids monitored through the gas (vacuum)/liquid interface

F. Maier, I. Niedermaier, and H.-P. Steinrück^{a)}

Lehrstuhl für Physikalische Chemie II, Friedrich-Alexander-Universität Erlangen-Nürnberg, Egerlandstr. 3, 91058 Erlangen, Germany

(Received 19 February 2017; accepted 10 April 2017; published online 1 May 2017)

This perspective analyzes the potential of X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy under ultrahigh vacuum (UHV) conditions to follow chemical reactions in ionic liquids *in situ*. Traditionally, only reactions occurring on solid surfaces were investigated by X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) *in situ*. This was due to the high vapor pressures of common liquids or solvents, which are not compatible with the required UHV conditions. It was only recently realized that the situation is very different when studying reactions in Ionic Liquids (ILs), which have an inherently low vapor pressure, and first studies have been performed within the last years. Compared to classical spectroscopy techniques used to monitor chemical reactions, the advantage of XPS is that through the analysis of their core levels all relevant elements can be quantified and their chemical state can be analyzed under well-defined (ultraclean) conditions. In this perspective, we cover six very different reactions which occur in the IL, with the IL, or at an IL/support interface, demonstrating the outstanding potential of *in situ* XPS to gain insights into liquid phase reactions in the near-surface region. © 2017 Author(s). All article content, except where otherwise noted, is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>). [<http://dx.doi.org/10.1063/1.4982355>]

I. INTRODUCTION

Ionic Liquids (ILs) are a comparably new class of liquid materials, which have attracted enormous scientific and industrial interest over the last decades.^{1–13} ILs are defined as molten salts, which (a) are composed entirely of cations and anions, (b) do not contain a molecular solvent, and (c) are liquid below 100 °C.¹⁴ The temperature of 100 °C is an arbitrarily chosen limit to distinguish ILs against high-temperature molten salts. In many cases, ILs have melting points or glass transition temperatures even below 25 °C; in this case, they are termed room-temperature ILs (RTILs). Many ILs are liquid and stable even up to their decomposition temperature (typically between 150 and 300 °C⁵), which opens a wide temperature window for their application and enables kinetic studies over a much larger range than for other liquids.

ILs are very promising candidates for many application areas ranging from synthesis¹⁵ and catalysis,^{6,16} green chemistry¹⁷ and biotechnology,¹⁸ electrochemistry^{3,19,20} and energy technology²¹ to analytics,²² separation technologies,²³ and hybrid materials.¹⁴ In many areas, ILs have now reached pilot- and large-scale industrial applications.¹ In particular, the BASIL process from BASF in 2002, which represents the first ton-scale industrial application of ILs in industry,²⁴ boosted IL research together with tremendous expectations for future applications in the first decade of the new millennium. The impressive variety of potential application areas is a direct consequence of the unique properties of ILs. These include the already mentioned low melting points, a wide

electrochemical stability window, and a microstructure that directly results from the complex interplay of interactions between the ions. In many cases, the cations and/or the anions employed are characterized by low charge density and low molecular symmetry, which prevents the formation of a stable crystal lattice. IL interionic interactions are characterized by long-range electrostatic as well as short-range intermolecular interactions such as hydrogen bonding, van der Waals, and π - π forces. This variety results in a manifold of low-energy conformations.²⁵ Modern IL cations are typically alkyl-substituted organic compounds, whereas the anions range from small inorganic ions such as halides to larger organic molecules. The structural diversity of ILs is the result of nearly unlimited possibilities to combine cations and anions with different chemical structure and thus different physico-chemical properties with respect to coordination behavior, solvation and miscibility properties, or electro-conductivity²⁶ and thermal stability,² to name a few. Organic chemistry allows for inserting alkyl chains at various positions and lengths into the ions, introducing functional groups for dedicated chemical interactions and reactions in the so-called task-specific ILs (TSILs).^{27,28} Furthermore, mixing more than one sort of cation and anion yields ternary, quaternary, or higher order systems, leading altogether to a virtually uncountable number of possible ILs.¹

In many IL applications, chemical reactions in ILs—or with components of the IL—play a key role. Consequently, there is a high demand for understanding the corresponding molecular reaction mechanism at the molecular level. This includes the identification of possible intermediates or by-products of the reaction as well as the reaction kinetics. For conventional solvents or liquids, the reaction progress

^{a)}hans-peter.steinrueck@fau.de

is routinely followed by a number of established analytical methods, including NMR, UV/Vis and IR spectroscopy, mass spectrometry, and calorimetric techniques.

Another powerful method to follow chemical reactions in ILs is X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS).^{29–31} In the past, this method has mostly been restricted to chemical reactions on solid surfaces^{32–42} because conventional XPS requires ultrahigh vacuum (UHV) conditions, which are not compatible with the high vapor pressure of most liquids and solvents. An exception is the use of dedicated experimental setups with differential pumping stages, which allow for performing XPS at the so-called near ambient pressure (NAP) conditions.^{43–45} Such systems are, for instance, used to follow processes up to pressures of 5 mbar and in exceptional cases even at higher pressures.⁴⁶ However, apart from one example, this approach is not in the focus of this perspective. We rather concentrate on liquids with an extremely low vapor pressure,^{4,5} that is, ILs. For ILs, one can make full use of the exceptional potential of XPS for reaction analysis. Unlike many other spectroscopic techniques, XPS is a quantitative method and enables direct *in situ* detection of all elements present in a sample, except hydrogen and helium. Furthermore, a change in the valence electron density of a particular atom, e.g., due to bond formation or change in chemical environment, is reflected in a so-called chemical shift of the corresponding core level. Changes in the peak intensity directly reflect the generation or consumption of reacting species or changes in molar density for species that do not directly take part in the reaction. These properties have earned XPS its second name ESCA, that is, electron spectroscopy for chemical analysis.

One further specific aspect of XPS is its surface sensitivity, which results from the small inelastic mean free path (IMFP) length of the emitted electrons of only a few nm, depending on their kinetic energy.³⁵ The resulting information depth, ID, defined as three times the IMFP, corresponds to the thickness of the near-surface region from which 95% of the emitted electrons originate. When using Al-K α radiation with 1486.6 eV, the ID of the relevant core levels of most ILs is 7–9 nm, for electron detection along the surface normal (0°). This ID corresponds to 10–15 layers of IL ion pairs of typical ILs. The surface sensitivity can be further enhanced by increasing the electron detection angle (e.g., by a factor of 6 at 80°) in angle-resolved XPS (ARXPS) or by adjusting the electron kinetic energy to ~100 eV in synchrotron radiation-based XPS (SRXPS). With such increased surface sensitivity, molecular orientation and segregation effects at the outermost surface layers can be determined.^{31,47}

First XPS work on ILs was performed in 2005 by the group of Peter Licence,⁴⁸ quickly followed by further XPS publications in 2006 by other groups, including that of the authors.^{49–53} Since then, this new field of “Ionic Liquid Surface Science” has established itself as an important discipline in ongoing IL research and many surface science techniques have successfully contributed to an increasingly detailed understanding not only of the IL/vacuum interface but also of the IL/support interface of ultrathin IL layers and of IL bulk properties.²⁹ In these initial studies,^{48–53} it was confirmed that vapor pressures of ILs are indeed sufficiently low to allow for the application of UHV conditions for a prolonged time without

either damage to the IL or any severe impact onto the base pressure of the UHV chamber. Furthermore, standard ILs proved to be stable under X-ray irradiation for a time sufficient for XPS investigations.

IL interfaces with a gas phase or with solids play a crucial role in the context of several processes. We are particularly interested in applications in heterogeneous catalysis, where ILs have led to completely new catalyst concepts such as the Supported Ionic Liquid Phase (SILP) and Solid Catalyst with Ionic Liquid Layer (SCILL) technologies.^{54–58} Both SILP and SCILL profit from the non-volatile IL character which allows for running reactions in gas streams without losing the liquid layer by evaporation. In the SILP system, an inert support material is coated with a very thin IL layer with the homogeneously dissolved catalyst. In SCILL systems, the solid catalyst material is immobilized on an oxide support and impregnated with an IL layer to enhance selectivity, product distribution, and yields.⁵⁸

When following chemical reactions in the IL bulk, one typically uses an emission angle of 0° at high kinetic energies in order to be as bulk sensitive as possible. Nevertheless, one has to be aware of the fact that only the topmost 10–15 layers contribute to the signal; in certain cases, this near-surface region might not be representative of the bulk.

Herein, we summarize *in situ* XPS measurements of surface reactions in ILs or with components of the IL, performed under UHV or near ambient pressure conditions. We focus on our own work and, where appropriate, give reference to the work by others concerning reactions or processes in ILs using surface science techniques. We explicitly do address only studies where the targeted process is a chemical reaction between different species but do not address physical processes such as a phase transition,^{59–61} adsorption or desorption,^{62–64} and diffusion^{65,66} or a reorganization.^{67–72} We also exclude studies where the reaction was not carried out *in situ*, that is, spectra were not recorded while the reaction proceeded, or the sample was moved to a different site in the XPS setup or was even removed from the XPS setup in order to carry out the reaction.^{73–77} We also do not address studies that incorporate electrochemical sample manipulation,^{66,67,69–71,78–86} electrodeposition of metal or organic layers from ILs,^{87–91} and IL decomposition^{84,92–102} or nanoparticle formation in ILs.^{62,75,103} Each of these topics was studied extensively and would justify a separate review.

In the following, we will address six different examples of chemical reactions which occur in ILs, with components of the ILs in the liquid phase, or at an IL/catalyst interface underneath a thick IL film. The first example addresses the most simple situation, namely, the reversible chemical reaction of a gas phase molecule, that is, CO₂, with a functionalized ionic liquid.¹⁰⁴ In the second example, the reaction of a gaseous strong acid with the anion of the IL is investigated. This Brønsted acid-base reaction results in anion metathesis of the IL, a step commonly used in IL synthesis.¹⁰⁵ The third example deals with the alkylation of an amine under solvent-free conditions by tethering the reactive groups to the cations and anions of an IL; the nucleophilic substitution reaction between the two functionalized ILs is sufficiently slow to allow for *ex situ* mixing and introduction into the UHV chamber, where the reaction is

triggered thermally.¹⁰⁶ The fourth example deals with dehydrogenation of a liquid organic hydrogen carrier (LOHC) tethered to an ionic headgroup of an IL, in a macroscopic film of the functionalized IL.¹⁰⁷ Dehydrogenation occurs at a catalytically active Pt foil, but can be monitored at the IL/vacuum interface, since product diffusion proved to be sufficiently fast. The fifth example addresses the thermochromic transition of an ionic liquid-based Co(II) complex from the tetrahedral to the octahedral configuration in the near-surface region.¹⁰⁸ We observed that the transformation occurs already around +4 °C, that is, well above the temperature of around -25 °C at which the bulk transition occurs. The sixth and last example concerns X-ray induced chemistry, that is, reduction or oxidation of metal complexes dissolved in ILs.¹⁰⁹

II. REACTION OF GAS PHASE MOLECULES WITH AN IL: CO₂ CAPTURE BY AN AMINE-FUNCTIONALIZED IL

Lowering or eliminating CO₂ emission is one of the present major challenges of mankind. One possible route for the removal of CO₂ from industrial flue gases is reversible chemical binding of CO₂, e.g., by amines such as aqueous monoethanolamine (MEA) solutions.¹¹⁰ In this context, ILs are considered as potential replacements for volatile amines due to their higher thermal stability and lower volatility.^{111–114} In 2002, Bates *et al.* proved that amine functionalization enhances the CO₂ uptake capacity of ILs considerably as compared to non-functionalized ILs.¹¹⁵ While a number of experimental and theoretical studies had been performed addressing different ILs with primary and secondary amines attached to the IL cation or anion in the bulk, a detailed investigation at the gas-liquid interface had been missing.

In order to elucidate CO₂ uptake in the near-surface region of ILs and to identify possible differences to the behavior in the bulk, a model IL, that is, di(hydroxyethyl)dimethylammonium taurinate (see left structure in Scheme 1) was exposed to CO₂ and the occurring chemical reactions were followed *in situ* by XPS.¹⁰⁴ This IL carries the amine functional group as part of the taurinate anion. The cation was chosen to mimic the hydroxyl functionality of MEA. In order to get as close as possible to realistic operation conditions of such ILs in flue gas streams with CO₂ partial pressures in the one hundred mbar regime,¹¹³ a near-ambient pressure (NAP) XPS setup was utilized that enables a local pressure at the sample of up to 1 mbar; notably, this pressure is of the same order of magnitude as the natural partial pressure of CO₂ in air of 0.4 mbar.

Scheme 1 shows the possible pathways upon reaction with CO₂. In the first step, CO₂ is inserted into the amine N–H bond which leads to the formation of a carbamic acid R–NCOOH. This step is denoted as the 1:1 mechanism because 1 mol CO₂ is bound per amine group (that is, per IL ion pair). If the reaction proceeds further with a proton transfer from the carbamic acid onto a second amine group, a carbamate species (R–NCOO⁻) and ammonium (R–NH₃⁺) are formed; this second step results in an overall uptake of 1 mol CO₂ per 2 mol of amine groups (2 IL ion pairs). This process is denoted as the 1:2 mechanism; it is less desirable than the 1:1 mechanism since only half of the amount of CO₂ is captured.

Before discussing the XPS data, it is important to analyze the N 1s binding energies of the involved reactants and products. All species with a neutral nitrogen atom, that is, amine, carbamate, and carbamic acid (atoms marked in blue in Scheme 1), have a very similar N 1s binding energy, and we are not able to differentiate them with the energy resolution of our setup. On the other hand, the N 1s signals of the positively charged ammonium of the non-reacting IL cations and of the ammonium zwitterion formed in the 1:2 mechanism (marked red in Scheme 1) appear at about 3 eV higher binding energy. This allows for differentiating between the two reaction mechanisms: for the 1:1 mechanism, no spectral changes are expected in the N 1s region because carbamic acid contains a neutral N species. In contrast, the successive reaction to carbamate in the 1:2 mechanism would lead to a shift of signal intensity from neutral N species towards the ionic ammonium species at higher binding energy because additional ammonium is formed.

Prior to the experiment, the neat IL was degassed in UHV for 1 h at 390 K. XP spectra measured after cooling to 310 K are shown in Figure 1 (black). In the N 1s region, two peaks of equal height were observed at 403.0 and 399.9 eV, resulting from the ammonium species in the cation and the amine group in the anion, respectively. In the O 1s region, one asymmetric broad peak is observed, which contains contributions of the two OH groups in the cation at 533.4 eV and the three oxygen atoms of the sulfonate group in the anion at 532.1 eV. From the quantitative analysis of all cation and anion components,¹¹⁶ including the S 2p and C 1s peaks, the stoichiometry of the IL is verified to within ±5%.

In the next step, this sample was exposed to a CO₂ pressure of 0.9 mbar at 310 K. The corresponding XP spectra measured at this pressure are also shown in Figure 1 (red), after correction for the overall signal attenuation by the CO₂ gas phase (for details see Ref. 104). As compared to the spectra prior to

SCHEME 1. Reaction mechanism of the amine-functionalized IL, with the reactive amine center as part of the taurinate anion. The cation does not take part in reaction. The anion reacts with 1 CO₂ molecule to form carbamic acid in the first step (1:1 mechanism). Carbamic acid may then form carbamate by transferring one proton to a second amine, forming ammonium (1:2 mechanism).¹⁰⁴

FIG. 1. (Black) N 1s and O 1s spectra of the neat IL di(hydroxyethyl) dimethylammonium taurinate after degassing; (red) N 1s and O 1s spectra during CO₂ dosage at a background pressure of 0.9 mbar, after scaling to account for signal damping by the gas phase.¹⁰⁴

CO₂ dosing, the ammonium N 1s peak at 403.0 eV increased by +15% ± 1%, and simultaneously the amine N 1s peak at 399.9 eV decreased by -15% ± 1%. These changes, which rapidly occurred within the first few minutes of CO₂ dosing, were accompanied by an increase of the IL-derived O 1s signals by +23% ± 3%. This increase is assigned to contributions from the COO groups of carbamic acid/carbamate formed in the near-surface region, which have similar binding energies as the OH and SO₃⁻ groups. The new peak at 537.6 eV stems from the CO₂ gas phase.

The quantitative analysis of the N 1s and O 1s peaks allows for determining the mean composition of the near-surface region, that is, within the XPS probing depth of 7–9 nm under a CO₂ pressure of 0.9 mbar. From the observed decrease of the neutral N 1s peak by -15% and the simultaneous increase of the ammonium N 1s peak by +15%, we conclude that ~0.15 mol CO₂ are bound to ~0.30 mol of the amine-functionalized IL anions via the carbamate/ammonium pathway, that is, the 1:2 mechanism. Considering the fact that one carbon dioxide molecule contains two oxygen atoms and one original IL ion pair contains five oxygen atoms, the increase of the O 1s signal by 23% translates into an average CO₂ uptake of ~0.58 mol CO₂ per ion pair (0.23 × 5/2). Since this total uptake of ~0.58 mol CO₂ is significantly larger than the amount of ~0.15 mol carbamate formed, we conclude that the additional amount of 0.58 - 0.15 = ~0.43 mol CO₂ is bound in the form of carbamic acid. Thus, 1 mol of the taurinate anion is transformed into ~0.15 mol carbamate as dianion, ~0.15 mol ammonium as zwitterion, and 0.43 mol carbamic acid, with 0.27 mol taurinate remaining unchanged.

XPS experiments for prolonged CO₂ exposure time and also spectra recorded after *ex situ* purging with CO₂ showed that a quasi-equilibrium situation is quickly reached in the near-surface region with the above composition of ~0.15 mol carbamate and ~0.43 mol carbamic acid. This remains initially unchanged even after ending CO₂ dosing, with the time required to return to the neat (CO₂-free) surface proportional to the initial CO₂ dosage time/pressure. We thus conclude that during CO₂ exposure, slow diffusion of CO₂-loaded molecules occurs from the near-surface region to the bulk, which serves

as a reservoir. After removal of the CO₂ gas phase, the process is reversed on a similar time scale and diffusion of CO₂-loaded molecules from the bulk to the near-surface occurs. Only after significant CO₂ depletion of the IL bulk, the composition in the near surface region changes back to that of the degassed neat IL.

To complement our *in situ* XPS experiments, which are sensitive to the near-surface region, we also performed CO₂ uptake experiments in the bulk under equilibrium conditions at 310 K by measuring external absorption isotherms and by infrared (IR) spectroscopy. Interestingly, we find that at low pressures much more CO₂ is stored in the near-surface region than in the bulk, whereas *in situ* XPS shows ~0.58 mol CO₂ per mol IL in the near-surface region already at 0.9 mbar, around 3 bars is required to obtain a similar amount in the bulk. In the near-surface region, carbamic acid is the dominating CO₂ carrier, whereas in the bulk (at least up to 1 bar), only carbamate is found as deduced from IR (see Ref. 104 for spectra). This difference is attributed to a different extent of charge screening by solvation for the singly charged carbamic acid (Scheme 1, center) and the doubly charged carbamate and ammonium (right) species. We propose that the latter are energetically stabilized in the bulk by the formation of a large solvation shell whereas the singly charged species are more easily stabilized in the near-surface region. This interpretation is in line with angle-resolved XP spectra that show neutral moieties being preferentially localized at the surface, while highly charged moieties have a strong tendency toward the bulk.¹¹⁷

III. REACTION OF AN IL WITH A GASEOUS ACID: ACID-BASE REACTIONS

While the first example concerned the reversible reaction/capture of CO₂ by an amine-based IL, the second example addresses an irreversible anion metathesis reaction of an IL.¹⁰⁵ This type of reaction is commonly used in IL synthesis, when the initial anion formed during the cation synthesis step (typically a halogenide) is exchanged with a desired one. The source of the desired anion may be the conjugate acid. We investigated the acid–base reaction between the IL 1-methyl-3-octyl-imidazolium chloride ([C₈C₁Im]Cl) and gaseous triflic acid (TfOH) (see Scheme 2). In the course of this reaction, a proton is transferred from the acid to the basic chloride ion of the IL. Thereby, triflate ([TfO]⁻) as new anion and gaseous HCl are formed. Under the applied UHV conditions, the reaction is influenced on the one hand by the acid strength and on the other hand by the differences in vapor pressure of TfOH and HCl; the latter is considerably more volatile. This example beautifully shows how XPS can comprehensively follow

SCHEME 2. Acid-base reaction of the IL [C₈C₁Im]Cl with volatile triflic acid (TfOH). Proton transfer leads to anion metathesis and the formation of the new IL [C₈C₁Im][TfO] and volatile HCl.¹⁰⁵

all processes taking place during the course of the reaction, namely, anion exchange, change in electronic structure of the cation that is not incorporated in the reaction step itself, and change in molar density.¹⁰⁵

The reaction is followed *in situ* by XPS while exposing a macroscopic film of $[\text{C}_8\text{C}_1\text{Im}]\text{Cl}$ of ≈ 0.2 mm thickness at room temperature to gaseous TfOH with a partial pressure of 1×10^{-6} mbar. This investigation was carried out in a standard UHV XPS system with a base pressure of 5×10^{-10} mbar. In Figure 2, the most relevant core level regions of pristine $[\text{C}_8\text{C}_1\text{Im}]\text{Cl}$ and after exposure of $[\text{C}_8\text{C}_1\text{Im}]\text{Cl}$ to TfOH for 80 and 170 min are depicted. For pristine $[\text{C}_8\text{C}_1\text{Im}]\text{Cl}$, the spectra contain only the expected C 1s (285.0/286.2 eV) and N 1s (401.6 eV; not shown) signals of the imidazolium cation and the spin-orbit split Cl 2p doublet (197.1/198.7 eV) of the anion. From the quantitative analysis of all cation and anion components, the stoichiometry of the IL is verified to within $\pm 5\%$. Upon exposure to TfOH, the ongoing acid-base reaction is reflected by new signals in the F 1s (688.5 eV), S 2p (169.7 eV), and O 1s (532.0 eV; not shown) regions, indicating the formation of the $[\text{TfO}]^-$ anion. A new peak is also found in the C 1s region (292.6 eV), which is assigned to the CF_3 groups of $[\text{TfO}]^-$. Parallel to the increase of the peaks characteristic of $[\text{TfO}]^-$, the Cl 2p doublet of the chloride ion decreased in intensity. After 80 min dosage, the $[\text{TfO}]^-$ signals increased to about 50% of the intensity of pure $[\text{C}_8\text{C}_1\text{Im}][\text{TfO}]$, and simultaneously the chloride intensity decreased to $\sim 50\%$. In other words, within the information depth of XPS, about half of the chloride of $[\text{C}_8\text{C}_1\text{Im}]\text{Cl}$ has reacted with TfOH yielding $[\text{C}_8\text{C}_1\text{Im}][\text{TfO}]$ and volatile HCl. After 170 min, the Cl 2p doublet has decreased to $\approx 9\%$ of its original intensity, reflecting more or less complete conversion of $[\text{C}_8\text{C}_1\text{Im}]\text{Cl}$ to $[\text{C}_8\text{C}_1\text{Im}][\text{TfO}]$. From the absence of any other Cl peaks, we deduce that no reactions other than the anion exchange (proton transfer) occur. To cross-check that the anion exchange had indeed occurred in the proposed way, we have included the spectra of a pure $[\text{C}_8\text{C}_1\text{Im}][\text{TfO}]$ film in Figure 2 (red); the comparison with the spectrum after 170 min exposure to TfOH shows perfect agreement of peaks positions and areas within the experimental error, confirming the proposed reaction pathway.

FIG. 2. Region spectra of $[\text{C}_8\text{C}_1\text{Im}]\text{Cl}$ at 0 min, 80 min, and 170 min TfOH dosage. Formation of $[\text{C}_8\text{C}_1\text{Im}][\text{TfO}]$ and HCl can be deduced from the reduction in Cl 2p peak intensity and the emergence of F 1s, S 2p, and C_{anion} signals. Spectra of pure $[\text{C}_8\text{C}_1\text{Im}][\text{TfO}]$ are shown in red for comparison.¹⁰⁵

The detailed analysis of the C 1s and also the N 1s (not shown) core levels allows for deriving further information: The C_{anion} peak at 292.6 eV is due to the $[\text{TfO}]^-$ anion formed by the ion exchange reaction. The C_{hetero} peak at ~ 286 eV stems from the five carbon atoms next to the nitrogen atoms (hetero atoms) of the imidazolium ring, and the C_{alkyl} peak at 285.0 eV from the seven carbon atoms of the octyl chain, which are bound to carbon and hydrogen only. The C_{alkyl} , C_{hetero} , and also the N 1s signals belong to the cation, which is not directly affected by the acid-base reaction. Their decrease by 12%–14% after 170 min exposure to TfOH reflects a decrease of the molar density (number of ion pairs per volume) during the reaction. This decrease is due the fact that the comparably small Cl^- anions are replaced by the significantly larger $[\text{TfO}]^-$ anions. Furthermore, the close inspection of the cation signals reveals a shift of the C_{hetero} peak and also the N 1s peak (for N 1s data see Ref. 105) towards higher binding energy by a total of 0.3 eV after 170 min exposure to TfOH. These shifts are attributed to differences in the interactions of the imidazolium head group with the small Cl^- and the larger $[\text{TfO}]^-$ anions.¹¹⁸

While our findings clearly demonstrate that nearly complete conversion of $[\text{C}_8\text{C}_1\text{Im}]\text{Cl}$ to $[\text{C}_8\text{C}_1\text{Im}][\text{TfO}]$ has occurred within the information depth of XPS (7–9 nm), one has to ask whether this acid-base reaction is restricted only to this near-surface region of the macroscopic IL film or also occurred in the bulk. To find out, the reacted IL (after 170 min exposure) was first stored under UHV for 30 h; XPS showed no changes of the chemical composition. In order to decrease viscosity and increase ion mobility, the IL film was then heated to 370 K for 60 min. XP spectra measured thereafter showed pronounced changes, that is, a decrease of peaks related to the $[\text{TfO}]^-$ anion and an increase of the Cl 2p doublet of the Cl^- anion. This observation indicates that the acid-base reaction indeed occurred predominantly in the region close to the surface. Upon heating, Cl^- anions diffuse from the IL bulk, where little or no reaction with TfOH had occurred to the near-surface region (i.e., to within the information depth of the XPS setup).

The observed behavior is particularly relevant when investigating chemical reactions in thin IL films used, e.g., in the SILP concept, where the reaction occurs at a dissolved catalyst complex. Depending on the experimental conditions, this reaction will be limited by the kinetics of the reaction itself or by the kinetics of the diffusion of the reactants to the catalyst complex, or by both. For a full understanding, both processes have to be characterized in detail, and XPS provides a perfect tool for such investigations.

IV. LIQUID-LIQUID REACTIONS: ALKYLATION OF AN AMINE-FUNCTIONALIZED IL

While dosing a gaseous or volatile liquid component onto a non-volatile IL film in the UHV chamber of an XPS system is a straightforward route to define the starting point of the reaction, carrying out a reaction between two liquid non-volatile components is more demanding. In 2012, we have demonstrated that the application of *in situ* XPS offers a new and general approach for monitoring ordinary liquid phase organic

SCHEME 3. Reaction mechanism of the alkylation of an amine-functionalized IL (N-IL) cation by the chlorinated anion of a second IL (Cl-IL), leading to the formation of an ammonium zwitterion and free chloride (Am-IL).¹⁰⁶

reactions and for deriving a mechanistic understanding.¹⁰⁶ In our approach, we drastically lowered the vapour pressures of the reactants by linking them before-hand to an ionic head group of an IL; notably, these IL head groups do not directly participate in the investigated reaction.^{47,106,119}

In the following, we discuss the liquid-liquid reaction between an IL with a reactive chloro-functionalized anion (Cl-IL) and an IL with a reactive amine cation (N-IL). The Cl-IL is 1-ethyl-3-methylimidazolium 4-chlorobutylsulfonate ($[\text{C}_2\text{C}_1\text{Im}][\text{ClC}_4\text{H}_8\text{SO}_3^-]$) and the N-IL is 1-methyl-3-(3'-dimethylaminopropyl)imidazolium trifluoromethylsulfonate ($[(\text{Me}_2\text{NC}_3\text{H}_6)\text{C}_1\text{Im}][\text{TfO}]$). In the course of this nucleophilic substitution reaction, the amine functionality of the N-IL is alkylated by the 4-chlorobutylsulfonate anion of the Cl-IL (Scheme 3) to form the new zwitterionic ammonium cation and a new chloride anion (Am-IL). As second product, $[\text{C}_2\text{C}_1\text{Im}][\text{TfO}]$ forms by the combination of the remaining non-reactive IL ions.

The reactive Cl-IL/N-IL mixture was prepared by dissolving both ILs in a 1:1 molar ratio in acetonitrile as a co-solvent to ensure proper mixing and by applying this solution repetitively to the surface of a polycrystalline Au foil that acted as an inert sample support for the following XPS investigation. The acetonitrile evaporated completely under ambient conditions in between the spreading steps onto the Au support and during pump-down when introducing the IL mixture into the UHV system. As the reaction rate is very low at room temperature,

the time-consuming transfer of the binary 1:1 mixture of the reactant ILs into the XP spectrometer and XPS investigations of the mixture prior to reaction were possible. To investigate the reaction, XPS spectra of the relevant core levels were measured directly after the transfer of the Cl-IL/N-IL mixture into the UHV system and after heating to 100 °C for 2 h in the spectrometer. The corresponding Cl 2p, N 1s, O 1s, and F 1s spectra in 0° emission are depicted in Figure 3 (black: before heating; red: after heating).

Upon heating, we found the alkylation of the amine functionality of the N-IL by the 4-chlorobutylsulfonate of the Cl-IL. The most obvious changes in the XP spectra occur in the Cl 2p and N 1s spectra due to changes in the chemical states, that is, covalently bound chlorine is transformed into chloride and the amine-functionality is alkylated to ammonium. In the N 1s spectra, the N_{amine} signal at 399.3 eV decreases to $44\% \pm 5\%$ of its former intensity, suggesting that 56% of the N-IL is converted to the alkylated product upon heating. At the same time, a new peak, which is assigned to the N_{ammon} species of the formed Am-IL, develops at 403.1 eV, that is, at the high binding energy side of the N_{imid} signal at 401.8 eV. The loss in N_{amine} intensity and the intensity of the new peak are balanced, indicating that this new peak is correctly assigned to the ammonium group in the zwitterionic reaction product (see Scheme 3).

The analysis of the Cl 2p region after heating indicates that $91\% \pm 5\%$ of covalently bound chlorine (Cl_{cov} ;

FIG. 3. Cl 2p, N 1s, O 1s, and F 1s XP spectra of the Cl-IL/N-IL mixture in 0° emission before (black lines) and after (red lines) heating to 100 °C for 2 h.¹⁰⁶

SCHEME 4. Parallel reactions: (a) Sultone formation and (b) formation of a 4-chlorobutylsulfonate ester by self-reaction of the 4-chlorobutylsulfonate anion.¹⁰⁶

Cl $2p_{3/2}$ at 200.2 eV) has reacted to free chloride (Cl_{ion} ; 197.0 eV), in contrast to the $\sim 56\% \pm 5\%$ conversion of the N-IL derived from the N 1s spectra. This difference indicates the occurrence of parallel reactions, which also consume covalently bound chlorine, in addition to the alkylation reaction. From the quantitative analysis of all core levels and the comparison to the behavior of the pure ILs, the formation of an anionic sulfonate ester and the elimination of volatile sultone from the anion $[\text{ClC}_4\text{H}_8\text{SO}_3]^-$ were identified as the relevant parallel reactions (Scheme 4). Both are self-reactions of the 4-chlorobutylsulfonate anion, in the former case intermolecularly, and in the latter the intramolecular reversal of the ring opening reaction employed to prepare the N-IL.¹²⁰

The quantification of the reactions results in the following yields: $\sim 56\%$ of $[\text{ClC}_4\text{H}_8\text{SO}_3]^-$ reacted within the desired alkylation process, $\sim 26\%$ was converted into 1,4-butane sultone, and the residual $\sim 18\%$ formed the sulfonate ester. The presence of Am-IL was also confirmed by an additional electrospray ionization mass spectrometry (ESI-MS) analysis of the reaction product after removal from the XPS chamber.

This example demonstrates that XPS as an atom specific, oxidation-state specific, and surface-selective analysis technique allows for determining significant mechanistically relevant information on the surface region of a “classical” nucleophilic substitution. The approach of lowering the vapor pressure of reactive units via linking to inert IL-tags can be transferred to other organic transformations, as will be demonstrated in Sec. V.

V. LIQUID-LIQUID REACTIONS: DEHYDROGENATION OF A LIQUID ORGANIC HYDROGEN CARRIER

This next example¹⁰⁷ was motivated by the research concerning liquid organic hydrogen carriers (LOHCs), which are considered as promising energy storage materials in a post fossil fuel society. The LOHC couple *N*-ethyl-carbazole (NEC)/*N*-ethyl-perhydrocarbazole (H_{12} -NEC) is one of the most studied model systems for hydrogen storage and thereby energy storage. In a ruthenium-catalyzed step, the hydrogen-lean NEC can be hydrogenated to the hydrogen-rich H_{12} -NEC, that is, it can take up 12 hydrogen atoms. In the reverse process, H_{12} -NEC can be dehydrogenated to NEC in a Pt- or Pd-catalyzed step at 500 to 550 K, under the release of 6 hydrogen molecules¹²¹ (Scheme 5, top reaction with $\text{R} = \text{R}^1$).

Detailed information on the dehydrogenation mechanism was deduced recently from surface science model studies under ultrahigh vacuum (UHV) conditions, that is, by a combination of XPS, thermal desorption spectroscopy (TDS), and time-resolved infrared reflection absorption spectroscopy (IRAS) on Pt(111) and Pd(111) surfaces and supported Pt- and Pd-clusters in the submonolayer to a few multilayer regime.¹²² Typical for the more reactive, non-equilibrium situation under the low coverage/low pressure experiments under UHV conditions, the individual reaction steps occur at significantly lower temperatures than those observed in real catalytic applications. Full dehydrogenation from H_{12} NEC to NEC already occurred until 380 K; in addition, starting at 390 K, an undesired abstraction of the ethyl chain via C-N scission was observed.

Our approach to get closer to the real situation for dehydrogenation at a catalyst-liquid interface under equilibrium conditions, while maintaining the same level of molecular insight, was to covalently link UHV-volatile carbazole derivatives to the imidazolium group of an IL ($-\text{R}^2$ in Scheme 5). The resulting ionic liquid-bound organic hydrogen carrier has negligible vapor pressure and thus allows for using surface

SCHEME 5. (Top) Hydrogenation/dehydrogenation of the functionalized liquid organic hydrogen carrier pair NEC (right) and H_{12} NEC (left), which reversibly can take up to 6 moles of molecular hydrogen. (center) Ethyl functionalization ($\text{R} = \text{R}^1$); (bottom) tethered to (functionalized with) a cationic imidazolium head group ($\text{R} = \text{R}^2$) that enables XPS investigation of the dehydrogenation in the liquid phase.¹⁰⁷

science techniques under UHV conditions. By *in situ* XPS, we followed the heterogeneously catalyzed reaction at a solid-liquid interface buried under a macroscopic liquid film (thickness about 0.1 mm). While this interface is not directly accessible by XPS due to the limited information depth of 7–9 nm, at the applied reaction temperatures, diffusion of molecules from the catalytic solid surface towards the outer near-surface region turned out to be fast enough on the time scale of the dehydrogenation experiment to reflect the equilibrium situation within the film.

The concept of the dehydrogenation experiment for the functionalized IL is sketched in Scheme 5 (with $R = R^2$, bottom). The perhydrocarbazole-functionalized imidazolium trifluoromethanesulfonate ionic liquid in the fully hydrogenated form is denoted PH-IL. It dehydrogenates to the fully dehydrogenated carbazole-functionalized imidazolium trifluoromethanesulfonate, denoted DH-IL. Thin films of these ILs were deposited on a Pt foil and a Au foil under ambient conditions and transferred to the UHV system.

In the first step, we investigated the pure perhydrogenated carbazole-functionalized IL, the dehydrogenated carbazole-functionalized IL, and an equimolar mixture of both in the liquid state at 350 K. As expected, the F 1s, O 1s, C 1s, and S 2p spectra of PH-IL and DH-IL are identical. However, pronounced differences are observed in the N 1s spectra (for details, see Figure 1 of Ref. 107): while the signal of the cationic imidazolium head group (N_{im}) is found at 402.2 eV for both ILs, the N 1s peaks of the dehydrogenated carbazole group (N_{DH}) and the perhydrogenated carbazole (N_{PH}) are observed at 400.2 and 398.9 eV, respectively (see Figure 4 that displays the following temperature-resolved reaction studies).

Within the experimental accuracy, the intensities of the N_{PH} and N_{DH} peaks relative to the N_{im} peaks of both ILs match the expected 1:2 ratio confirming the nominal stoichiometries. The difference of 1.3 eV in the N 1s binding energies of PH-IL and the DH-IL reflects the differences in the chemical state of the hydrogenated and dehydrogenated species. It is large

enough that the peaks can be well separated and thus allows one to unequivocally follow the dehydrogenation of PH-IL to DH-IL by the changes in the N 1s region.

As the next step, we studied the dehydrogenation reaction of the PH-IL deposited on a Pt foil as catalytically active support. In the course of the experiment, the sample was heated from 350 to 550 K in steps of 5 or 10 K; at each temperature, the sample was kept for 50 min and XP spectra were collected (this stepwise heating corresponds to a mean heating rate of $\sim 0.002 \text{ K s}^{-1}$). The corresponding data are depicted in Figure 4(a). To compare dehydrogenation without a catalyst, the identical experiment was performed for PH-IL on a Au foil as support. This system should display a much lower catalytic activity than Pt. The corresponding N 1s spectra are shown in Figure 4(b).

On the Pt foil, the N 1s spectra below 440 K show only the N_{PH} peak at 398.9 eV, in addition to the N_{im} signal at 402.2 eV. At $\sim 450 \text{ K}$ (red), the N_{PH} signal starts to decrease and at the same time the N_{DH} signal develops as a shoulder around 400.2 eV, indicating the onset of dehydrogenation. With increasing temperature, the N_{DH} shoulder develops into a well-resolved peak, and the N_{PH} peak continues to decrease. The conversion from the PH-IL to the DH-IL is completed at $\sim 520 \text{ K}$ (red). At this temperature, the spectrum is identical to that of the neat DH-IL on a gold foil measured at 500 K (dashed spectrum at top of Figure 4(a)). At higher temperatures, a small decrease of the N_{im} peak indicates the onset of IL decomposition; this interpretation is supported by the detection of imidazolium and its cracking products by QMS in the gas phase at 550 K and is in line with a thermal gravimetric analysis, where a decomposition temperature of 557 K was found (see Experimental Section in the original publication¹⁰⁷).

The reference experiments on the Au foil show a similar conversion of N_{PH} to N_{DH} as on the Pt foil, albeit at significantly higher temperature. The quantitative analyses of the thermal evolution on the Pt- and Au-foils are shown in Figures 5(a) and 5(b), respectively. The normalized N_{PH} and N_{DH} intensities, that is, $r_{PH} = N_{PH}/(N_{PH} + N_{DH})$ and

FIG. 4. N 1s region spectra of PH-IL on a catalytically active Pt foil (left) and on an inert Au foil (right) are monitored in temperature-resolved measurements with T increasing from 350 to 550 K (bottom to top). The onset of dehydrogenation can be determined by a shift from the N_{PH} signal to the N_{DH} position. It is observed at 450 K (bottom red spectrum) for the catalyzed situation and at 500 K (bottom green spectrum) for the non-catalyzed situation. Dehydrogenation is finished at 520 K (catalyzed situation, top red spectrum) and at 540 K (non-catalyzed situation, top green spectrum).¹⁰⁷

FIG. 5. Top: Normalized intensities of N_{PH} and N_{DH} signals vs. temperature on a Pt foil (a) and on a Au foil (b). Bottom: Molecular hydrogen ($m/z = 2$) evolution curves for PH-IL and DH-IL vs. temperature on Pt foil (c) and on Au foil (d).¹⁰⁷

$r_{DH} = N_{DH}/(N_{PH} + N_{DH})$, are obtained from the spectra in Figure 4 by curve fitting. The comparison clearly shows the earlier dehydrogenation onset (450 K on Pt vs. 500 K on Au) and lower temperature of 50% conversion (480 K on Pt vs. 515 K on Au) on the Pt support. The temperatures found are close to those observed for conventional (N-ethyl)perhydrocarbazole dehydrogenation under realistic reactor conditions.¹²¹ The similar reaction temperatures thus provide a clear indication that the imidazolium IL tag linked to the perhydrocarbazole unit does not have a major impact on the dehydrogenation reaction of the latter under liquid phase conditions.

Upon dehydrogenation of the perhydrocarbazole unit of the PH-IL, molecular hydrogen is released to the gas phase. The corresponding hydrogen evolution was investigated in a separate experiment by thermal desorption spectroscopy (TDS) of dihydrogen ($m/z = 2$) with heating rates between 0.04 and 0.14 Ks^{-1} ; notably, this heating rate is 20 to 70 times faster than the mean heating rate during XPS. The corresponding spectra for PH-IL and for comparison also for DH-IL are shown at the bottom of Figure 5 for both the Pt and Au supports. On Pt, the maximum H_2 evolution for PH-IL occurred at 498 K, and on Au at 554 K, following the trends observed by XPS. The maxima are shifted to higher temperatures as compared to the 50% conversion temperature derived from XPS by 20–40 K due to the higher heating rates in TDS compared to XPS. From the observation of one dominating peak in the molecular desorption of hydrogen (the broad shoulder is attributed to desorption from the sample holder), we conclude that dehydrogenation of the PH-IL to the DH-IL occurs within a narrow temperature window (~ 50 K), which does not allow for resolving individual dehydrogenation steps. This observation is in line with our *in situ* XPS analysis of the dehydrogenation, where no distinct dehydrogenation steps were seen either.

To conclude, this example demonstrated that at reaction temperatures, where diffusion of reactants and products is fast enough, the composition of the near surface region, which is directly probed by XPS, is representative of the bulk composition changes due to dehydrogenation at the catalyst/IL interface.

VI. LIQUID-LIQUID REACTIONS: THERMOCHROMIC TRANSFORMATION OF A METAL COMPLEX

As outlined in the Introduction, one important application of ILs is SILP catalysis.⁵⁷ In SILP,^{54,123–125} transition metal (TM) complexes are commonly employed as catalytically active species, with a thin IL film serving as solvent for both reactants and metal complex. An interesting situation arises when the ILs provide ligands themselves, with much higher concentrations than achieved in traditional molecular solvents. For ILs with one ion serving as a ligand of the desired complex, one can avoid ligand replacement by other solvent molecules. As has been shown in the example of CO_2 capture by an amine-functionalized IL, the near-surface region chemistry can be quite different to the bulk one due to the presence of the vacuum (gas) boundary.¹⁰⁴ This difference becomes particularly relevant for SILP systems, where the surface area is large compared to the bulk. We thus extend our reaction studies to a metal-ligand complex reaction under thermodynamic equilibrium conditions.¹⁰⁸

For this purpose, XPS was applied to the dynamical metal complex system based on an IL with the doubly negatively charged $[Co(II)(NCS)_4]^{2-}$ as anion;¹²⁶ for this anion, Osborne *et al.*¹²⁷ reported a thermochromic transformation to the doubly negatively charged $[Co(II)(NCS)_6]^{4-}$ anion upon cooling. The scheme of the corresponding complex equilibrium is depicted in Scheme 6. At room temperature, the equilibrium lies on the left hand side, as witnessed by the deep blue colour of the tetrahedrally coordinated cobalt anion. Cooling shifts the equilibrium to the right, as evident from the red colour of the octahedrally coordinated complex at around -40 °C.¹²⁷

In order to elucidate the dynamical behavior, we studied a mixture of the IL di(1-ethyl-3-methylimidazolium) tetrathiocyanatocobaltate(II) ($[C_2C_1Im]_2[Co(II)(NCS)_4]$, IL-2) with an excess of 1-ethyl-3-methylimidazolium thiocyanate ($[C_2C_1Im][SCN]$, IL-1) with a molar ratio of 1:3 yielding a new IL with nominal composition $[C_2C_1Im]_5[Co(II)(NCS)_4][SCN]_3$ (IL-3). For clarity, we denote the free thiocyanate anions as “[SCN]⁻,” and the thiocyanate ligands as “[NCS]⁻,” since they are coordinated to the Co^{2+}

SCHEME 6. Top: neat metal complex equilibrium. Bottom: Representation of the ILs involved and color-coding of the atoms with specific binding energy values discussed in the text: N 1s imidazolium (grey) = 401.8 eV; N 1s free $[\text{SCN}]^-$ (bright blue) = 397.8 eV \approx N 1s $[\text{Co(NCS)}_6]^{4-}$; N 1s $[\text{Co(NCS)}_4]^{2-}$ (dark blue) = 398.5 eV; S $2p_{3/2}$ free $[\text{SCN}]^-$ (bright green) = 162.2 eV \approx S $2p_{3/2}$ $[\text{Co(NCS)}_6]^{4-}$; S $2p_{3/2}$ $[\text{Co(NCS)}_4]^{2-}$ (orange) = 162.9 eV.¹⁰⁸

center via the negatively charged nitrogen end.¹²⁶ For this IL mixture, a color change from blue to red was observed in the same temperature range as has been reported in literature, with a mid-transition temperature around -25°C . Due to the thermochromic transition, the mixture IL-3 ($[\text{C}_2\text{C}_1\text{Im}]^+_2[\text{Co(NCS)}_4]^{2-} + 3[\text{C}_2\text{C}_1\text{Im}]^+[\text{SCN}]^-$) transforms to a new mixture IL-4 ($[\text{C}_2\text{C}_1\text{Im}]^+_4[\text{Co(II)(NCS)}_6]^{4-} + [\text{C}_2\text{C}_1\text{Im}]^+[\text{SCN}]^-$). Notably, the latter has an excess of one IL-1 ion pair per formed octahedral complex.

Possible differences of the behavior in the bulk and in the near-surface region were studied by measuring temperature-dependent XP spectra of the neat ILs, IL-1 and IL-2, and the mixture IL-3 from room temperature, down to -75°C . We concentrated on the N 1s and S 2p regions because the thiocyanate signals of the cobalt-coordinated ligands and of the free anions can be easily monitored; the corresponding carbon signal cannot be separated from the signal of imidazolium ring. In Figure 6(a), the N 1s and S 2p spectra at 24°C and -10°C are compared.

For IL-1 and IL-2, the peaks of the thiocyanate nitrogen in free $[\text{SCN}]^-$ at 397.8 and in the cobalt-bound $[\text{NCS}]^-$ ligands at 398.5 eV are clearly separated from the imidazolium peak at 401.8 eV. The S 2p peaks of IL-1 are observed at 162.2 eV ($2p_{3/2}$ component), the corresponding peak of IL-2 at 162.9 eV. Both show no significant change with temperature. The thiocyanate peaks of IL-3 at 24°C are significantly broader than observed for IL-1 and IL-2. The anion N 1s signal (black spectrum in Figure 6) can be fitted with a peak due to cobalt-bound thiocyanate in $[\text{Co(NCS)}_4]^{2-}$ at 398.5 eV and a peak due to free $[\text{SCN}]^-$ at 397.8 eV, with the nominal molar ratio of 4:3 expected for the IL-2:IL-1 = 1:3 mixture.

Upon moderate cooling of the mixture IL-3 to -10°C , which is above the color transition temperature of -25°C , a pronounced narrowing and intensity loss of the $[\text{SCN}]^-$ -related N 1s and S 2p peaks (green spectra of IL-3 in Figure 6) is observed, yielding FWHM values similar to those observed for IL-1. From a slow cooling and heating experiment from $+24^\circ\text{C}$ to 0°C and back to $+24^\circ\text{C}$ in 2°C steps (not shown), a fully reversible behavior with a transition temperature of

4°C is deduced, indicating a transition from the tetrahedral to the octahedral complex in the near-surface region probed by XPS. This temperature is $\sim 30^\circ\text{C}$ higher than the transition temperature of -25°C in the bulk. At $+4^\circ\text{C}$, beneath the XPS probing depth of 9 nm, free $[\text{SCN}]^-$ and $[\text{Co(II)(NCS)}_4]^{2-}$

FIG. 6. (a) N 1s (left) and S 2p (right) region spectra of IL-1, IL-2, and IL-3 measured in normal emission at 24°C (black) and at -10°C (red). The dashed lines show binding energy positions referenced to imidazolium nitrogen at 401.8 eV; moreover, deconvolution of the N 1s $[\text{SCN}]^-$ signal of IL-3 at 24°C is shown as discussed in the text. (b) Scaled comparison of the Co 2p spectra of IL-3 in normal emission. The red spectrum is the average of the -10°C and -30°C spectra, scaled to the same height as the 24°C spectrum.¹⁰⁸

anions are still present as clearly shown by the deep blue color of the liquid film covering the sample holder; at $-30\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, the IL-3 film on the sample holder has changed its color from blue to a red appearance, as witnessed by visual inspection.

Additional information on the transformation from the tetrahedral to the octahedral cobalt complex can be derived from the Co 2p spectra of IL-3. In Figure 6(b), the normal emission Co 2p spectrum at $+24\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and the average of the Co 2p spectra at $-10\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $-30\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ (averaged to obtain better statistics) are shown without background subtraction. The shape of the spectrum at $+24\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ is identical to that of IL-2 (which does not show any changes upon cooling); the Co $2p_{1/2}$ branch from 810 to 795 eV, and the Co $2p_{3/2}$ branch from 795 to 778 eV both show multiplet splitting, as expected for an open shell Co(II)-system. Upon cooling to $-10\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, the Co 2p spectral appearance of IL-3 changes considerably, that is, changes in shape and differential shifts of the maxima in the $2p_{1/2}$ and $2p_{3/2}$ branches by about -0.6 and -1.1 eV to lower binding energy, respectively, are observed. This behavior clearly indicates a transformation of the complex. Since no further spectral changes occur upon cooling to $-30\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and below, where the IL-3 film turned fully red, we attribute the $-10\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ spectrum shown in Figure 6(b) to the octahedral $[\text{Co}(\text{II})(\text{NCS})_6]^{4-}$ complex being dominantly present in the near-surface region probed by XPS. It is important to note that upon cooling, we also observe a pronounced decrease of the overall Co 2p signal, to about 40% of the original signal at $24\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$; this indicates a decrease in density of the Co complex in the near-surface region. As one possible explanation, we propose that in order to be stabilized at temperatures above the bulk transition temperature, the four times negatively charged octahedral $[\text{Co}(\text{II})(\text{NCS})_6]^{4-}$ complex with its four imidazolium cations is solvated by additional $[\text{SCN}]^-$ anions. The resulting excess of $[\text{SCN}]^-$ anions (with their corresponding cations) are weakly bound to the octahedral complex in the near-surface region. A solvation shell with, e.g., eight to ten weakly bound $[\text{SCN}]^-$ ions would be consistent with the Co 2p signal decrease. Notably, the changes of the Co 2p signal go along with a loss of surface enrichment of the $[\text{SCN}]^-$ anions upon cooling.

In conclusion, we studied the temperature-driven transition of an ionic liquid-based Co(II) complex from the tetrahedral to the octahedral configuration in the near-surface region. We observed that the thermochromic transformation from the tetrahedral $[\text{Co}(\text{II})(\text{NCS})_4]^{2-}$ complex to the octahedral complex occurs already around $+4\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, that is, well above the temperature of around $-25\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ at which the bulk transition occurs. The transition goes along with a pronounced decrease of the complex density in the near-surface region, which is attributed to the formation of a weakly bound $[\text{SCN}]^-$ solvation shell around a more tightly bound solvation shell of cations around the $[\text{Co}(\text{II})(\text{NCS})_6]^{4-}$ anion, that is, an effective dilution of the complex.

At this point, we want to stress that such surface-induced phenomena could be of high relevance for all concepts, where high surface area materials are applied. While these effects are very difficult to discern using bulk analytic methods, we have demonstrated that for ionic liquid-based systems, surface sensitive XPS allows one to access such changes in detail.

VII. X-RAY INDUCED LIQUID PHASE REACTIONS: REDUCTION AND OXIDATION OF PT-COMPLEXES

This last chapter addresses potential influence of the X-rays applied in XPS on the investigated ionic liquids or metal complexes. The X-ray beam used in the XP experiment can be employed to carry out reduction or oxidation reactions in transition metal complexes, as demonstrated below for compounds containing Pt complexes.¹⁰⁹

Various salt solutions of different Pt(II)- and Pt(IV)-complexes undergo structural changes during XPS, which can be identified through spectral changes of the measured spectra caused by prolonged X-ray irradiation.¹⁰⁹ Herein, we focus on two representative examples: The anionic Pt(IV)-complex of $[\text{C}_2\text{C}_1\text{Im}]_2[\text{PtCl}_6]$ dissolved in the IL $[\text{C}_2\text{C}_1\text{Im}][\text{EtOSO}_3]$ was monitored during X-ray induced reduction to a Pt(II) species, and the cationic Pt(II) complex of $[\text{Pt}(\text{NH}_3)_4][\text{Tf}_2\text{N}]_2$ dissolved in $[\text{C}_2\text{C}_1\text{Im}][\text{Tf}_2\text{N}]$ was investigated while it underwent X-ray induced oxidation to a Pt(IV) species. We focus on the Pt 4f doublet corresponding to the central metal atom, which was recorded as a probe for Pt oxidation state.

The reduction of $[\text{C}_2\text{C}_1\text{Im}]_2[\text{PtCl}_6]$ in $[\text{C}_2\text{C}_1\text{Im}][\text{EtOSO}_3]$ induced by X-rays can be followed in Figure 7 (left), where the Pt 4f region is depicted for increasing exposure to Al K α radiation. Spectrum (a) measured immediately after switching on the X-rays is dominated by the Pt(IV) signal at 74.8 eV, with a minor Pt(II) peak at 72.6 eV (only the binding energies of the Pt $_{7/2}$ level are denoted); it corresponds to a total exposure time of 5 min. With increasing X-ray exposure, the small Pt(II) signal grows and simultaneously the Pt(IV) signal decreases: After 68 min, the two signals are roughly equal in intensity; for the highest exposure of 414 min, the Pt(IV) signal has nearly vanished, and the spectrum is completely dominated by the Pt(II) signal. An additional measurement (not shown) after ~ 15 h, without further X-ray exposure, showed no changes, which is strong evidence for an irreversible reduction of Pt(IV) to Pt(II). Another interesting observation is the dependence of Cl 2p signals on X-ray exposure (not shown). For the first spectrum with only minor exposure to X-rays, the Cl:Pt ratio of 5.5:1 matches the nominal ratio of 6:1 within the margin of error. However, upon prolonged X-ray irradiation, the ratio decreases to 1.2:1 after 414 min. This loss of Cl signal indicates that not only an X-ray induced reduction of Pt(IV) to Pt(II) takes place but also in addition X-ray induced ligand exchange and removal via chloride oxidation to chlorine radicals occur.

The oxidation of Pt(II) to Pt(IV) induced by X-rays was observed for the solution of $[\text{Pt}^{\text{II}}(\text{NH}_3)_4][\text{Tf}_2\text{N}]_2$ in $[\text{C}_2\text{C}_1\text{Im}][\text{Tf}_2\text{N}]$. The corresponding time-dependent Pt 4f spectra are shown in Figure 7 (right). Directly after introducing the sample into the X-ray beam, the Pt $4f_{7/2}$ spectrum (e) is dominated by the Pt(II) signal at 73.5 eV, with a minor Pt(IV) peak at 75.7 eV. With increasing X-ray exposure, the Pt(IV) peak gains intensity, while the Pt(II) peak decreases ((f) and (g)). In the course of this process, the total Pt 4f intensity remains unchanged. Interestingly, in contrast to the previous example, the Pt(II) component partly recovers after removing the sample from the X-ray beam (h). This could

FIG. 7. (Left) Pt 4f region of the 4.86 mol% solution of $[\text{C}_2\text{C}_1\text{Im}]_2[\text{PtCl}_6]$ in $[\text{C}_2\text{C}_1\text{Im}][\text{EtOSO}_3]$ in 0° emission right after introducing the sample in the X-ray beam (a), after 68 min (b), after overall 134 min (c), and after overall 414 min X-ray exposure time (d). (right) Pt 4f region of a 4.45 mol% solution of $[\text{Pt}(\text{NH}_3)_4][\text{Tf}_2\text{N}]_2$ in $[\text{C}_2\text{C}_1\text{Im}][\text{Tf}_2\text{N}]$ in 0° emission right after introducing the sample in the X-ray beam (e), after 140 min (f), and after 314 min (g) of X-ray exposure, and after ~ 18 h without X-ray irradiation (h). Structures of both Pt complexes and their counter ions are given at the top. The differences in Pt 4f BE between $[\text{C}_2\text{C}_1\text{Im}]_2[\text{PtCl}_6]$ and $[\text{Pt}(\text{NH}_3)_4][\text{Tf}_2\text{N}]_2$ for the respective Pt(II) and Pt(IV) species are due to the fact that in $[\text{C}_2\text{C}_1\text{Im}]_2[\text{PtCl}_6]$, Pt is the center of the anionic complex, while for $[\text{Pt}(\text{NH}_3)_4][\text{Tf}_2\text{N}]_2$, Pt is part of the cation.¹⁰⁹

indicate a back reaction to Pt(II). It is also possible that diffusion of unreacted Pt(II) species from the bulk to the surface occurs.

Notably, similar studies were carried out by the Licence group: Already in 2005, Smith *et al.* noticed the reduction of a Pd(II) complex dissolved in an IL on prolonged X-ray irradiation.⁴⁸ In 2012, Taylor *et al.* reported on the oxidation of ferrocenium-based ILs upon irradiation with electrons during charge compensation,¹²⁸ and in 2016, Longo *et al.* published the X-ray induced reduction of Sb(V) to Sb(III) and further to Sb(0) in an IL with a Sb based anion.¹²⁹

VIII. CONCLUSIONS AND OUTLOOK

We have demonstrated by our case studies that a large variety of chemical reactions and reaction mechanisms of different complexity are accessible when using *in situ* XPS to investigate the liquid phase chemistry of ionic liquids. Our studies included CO_2 -capture reactions, acid-base reactions, nucleophilic substitution reactions, dehydrogenation reactions of IL-tagged liquid organic hydrogen carriers, a thermochromic

transformation of a complex equilibrium, and X-ray induced reactions.

The described investigations proved the high level of in-depth insights concerning reaction mechanisms. However, they also revealed limits and needs for further improvements. First, mainly the static, steady-state situation before and after the reaction at one specific temperature was measured, and no *in situ* real-time experiments during fast reactions were possible due to long measuring times. Second, when studying liquids, other effects have to be considered, which are typically absent on the time scale of reactions at solid surfaces. In two of the studied examples, vertical diffusion, that is, exchange of reactants and products between the near-surface region and the bulk, played a considerable role. For the acid-base reaction, diffusion was slow at room temperature and the reaction thus occurred mainly in the near-surface region, as evidenced by the change in reactant and product concentration upon post-reaction annealing. For the dehydrogenation reaction, diffusion at the reaction temperature around 200°C was fast enough such that the product was uniformly distributed in the IL film; therefore, the dehydrogenation at the catalyst buried under a macroscopically thick IL film surface could be directly monitored via the product concentration at the IL/vacuum interface. For situations, where diffusion and reaction occur on comparable time scales, a more complicated situation arises. The exchange between surface and bulk in the course of the described reactions uncovers a third aspect, which is related to the limited probing depth of XPS. Since the measurements were performed using laboratory Al $K\alpha$ radiation with a photon energy of 1486.6 eV, the information depth was restricted to the topmost 7–9 nm. In two examples, that is, the CO_2 capture reaction and the thermochromic transition, we found that the chemistry close to the surface differed from that in the bulk. It would thus be highly desirable to increase information depth in order to detect at which thickness the transition from the interface-dominated behavior to the bulk behavior occurs.

Based on these considerations, we see several important directions and challenges for applying XPS for *in situ* reaction studies in ionic liquid systems:

- (1) *In situ* real-time measurements during the reactions at various temperatures, as a function of time, are possible with improved experimental setups, e.g., with a new unique XPS apparatus in our lab.⁶⁰ This setup is the first of its kind and is equipped with two electron analyzers for detection at 0° and 80° . It enables simultaneously studying the bulk and the surface of the IL, by angle-resolved XPS, without the need of rotating the liquid sample. In the “snapshot mode,” full XP spectra of a specific core level can be measured with very short measuring times, down to only 1 s for levels with high cross section. Alternatively, one can use high-flux synchrotron radiation, which has the additional benefit of better energy resolution. Here, beam damage has to be very carefully considered due to the small focus of the X-ray beam at most beamlines. Fast measurements allow for following reactions in real time, that is, while they occur. By monitoring the temperature dependence of the relevant signals in isothermal experiments

at various temperatures, the activation energy of the rate-limiting step can be derived from an Arrhenius analysis, as has been demonstrated for chemical reactions on solid surfaces.⁴²

- (2) In order to increase the information depth, X-rays with higher photon energy, either from specific lab sources with, e.g., monochromatized Ag $L\alpha$ radiation,¹³⁰ or from corresponding beamlines at synchrotron facilities offer highly promising potential. An alternative is the simultaneous use of complementary bulk-sensitive techniques that can be coupled to the XPS setup, such as UV-vis or IR-absorption spectroscopy, X-ray scattering, conductivity measurements, or mass spectrometry, in order to follow changes in the bulk in the course of the reaction. Both approaches will make XPS of ionic liquids an even more generally applicable spectroscopic tool.
- (3) One important challenge when studying liquid systems is diffusion from the interface to the bulk and vice versa. As a consequence, the decrease or increase of a signal cannot be simply directly assigned to a chemical reaction, but one also has to take into account the kinetics of the diffusion of reactants and products, which opens a very interesting research field by itself, e.g., by pulsed experiments. Here one could envisage, e.g., pulsed deposition of a species onto an ionic liquid surface, following the change of XPS signals of this species over time due to diffusion effects.
- (4) Another very important area would be quantitative *in situ* studies of chemical reactions in ILs under electrochemical conditions; the interest in this area is driven by their huge potential in electrochemical applications.^{3,20,131} Presently, one often lacks a detailed mechanistic understanding of the ongoing reactions or processes at the IL/electrode interface. In particular, the spectroscopic investigation using UHV-based surface science methods still is at its infancy due to a number of experimental challenges. Licence *et al.*,^{66,83} Wein-garth *et al.*,^{84,132} and Wibowo *et al.*^{90,91} demonstrated that two-electrode and three-electrode chemical cells, mounted on appropriate sample holders, allow for *in situ* XPS under an applied potential in mostly static experiments. Other interesting studies in this context were performed by Fukui *et al.*,¹³³ and Suzer *et al.*⁷⁸ We envisage that combining more advanced electrochemical cells with real-time *in situ* XPS under electrochemical condition will become an important field in the future.

At the end of this perspective, we would like to emphasize again that with the XPS investigations of ionic liquids starting around 2005, a new method for reaction studies in the liquid state and particularly at liquid surfaces has become available that was not possible in such way before.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This project has received funding from the European Research Council (ERC) under the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme (Grant

Agreement No. 693398—ILID). The authors thank Claudia Kolbeck, Nicola Taccardi, Peter S. Schulz, Peter Wasserscheid, Jing Li, Thomas Drewello, Natalia Paape, Matthias Bahlmann, Christian Papp, Wei Wei, Sandra Krick Calderón, Mathias Grabau, Takashi Matsuda, Johannes Schwegler, Ben May, Francesco Greco, and Radha Bhuin who contributed to the results presented in this paper.

- ¹N. V. Plechkova and K. R. Seddon, *Chem. Soc. Rev.* **37**, 123 (2008).
- ²P. Wasserscheid and T. Welton, *Ionic Liquids in Synthesis* (Wiley-VCH, Weinheim, 2008).
- ³F. Endres and S. Z. El Abedin, *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.* **8**, 2101 (2006).
- ⁴P. Wasserscheid, *Nature* **439**, 797 (2006).
- ⁵M. J. Earle, J. M. S. S. Esperanca, M. A. Gilea, J. N. C. Lopes, L. P. N. Rebelo, J. W. Magee, K. R. Seddon, and J. A. Widegren, *Nature* **439**, 831 (2006).
- ⁶T. Welton, *Coord. Chem. Rev.* **248**, 2459 (2004).
- ⁷R. P. Swatloski, S. K. Spear, J. D. Holbrey, and R. D. Rogers, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **124**, 4974 (2002).
- ⁸P. R. Gifford and J. B. Palmisano, *J. Electrochem. Soc.* **134**, 610 (1987).
- ⁹A. P. Doherty and C. A. Brooks, *Electrochim. Acta* **49**, 3821 (2004).
- ¹⁰S. Eisele, M. Schwarz, B. Speiser, and C. Tittel, *Electrochim. Acta* **51**, 5304 (2006).
- ¹¹R. Barhdadi, C. Courtinard, J. Y. Nedelec, and M. Troupel, *Chem. Commun.* **2003**, 1434.
- ¹²P. Wasserscheid and W. Keim, *Angew. Chem., Int. Ed.* **39**, 3772 (2000).
- ¹³K. Binnemans, *Chem. Rev.* **105**, 4148 (2005).
- ¹⁴T. Torimoto, T. Tsuda, K. Okazaki, and S. Kuwabata, *Adv. Mater.* **22**, 1196 (2010).
- ¹⁵C. Chiappe and D. Pieraccini, *J. Phys. Org. Chem.* **18**, 275 (2005).
- ¹⁶J. P. Hallett and T. Welton, *Chem. Rev.* **111**, 3508 (2011).
- ¹⁷R. A. Sheldon, *Green Chem.* **7**, 267 (2005).
- ¹⁸C. Roosen, P. Müller, and L. Greiner, *Appl. Microbiol. Biotechnol.* **81**, 607 (2008).
- ¹⁹M. Armand, F. Endres, D. R. MacFarlane, H. Ohno, and B. Scrosati, *Nat. Mater.* **8**, 621 (2009).
- ²⁰M. V. Fedorov and A. A. Kornyshev, *Chem. Rev.* **114**, 2978 (2014).
- ²¹D. R. MacFarlane *et al.*, *Energy Environ. Sci.* **7**, 232 (2014).
- ²²J. L. Anderson, D. W. Armstrong, and G. T. Wei, *Anal. Chem.* **78**, 2892 (2006).
- ²³D. Han and K. H. Row, *Molecules* **15**, 2405 (2010).
- ²⁴M. Maase and K. Massonne, *ACS Symp. Ser.* **902**, 126 (2005).
- ²⁵P. A. Hunt, I. R. Gould, and B. Kirchner, *Aust. J. Chem.* **60**, 9 (2007).
- ²⁶D. R. Macfarlane, M. Forsyth, P. C. Howlett, J. M. Pringle, J. Sun, G. Annat, W. Neil, and E. I. Izgorodina, *Acc. Chem. Res.* **40**, 1165 (2007).
- ²⁷J. H. Davis, *Chem. Lett.* **33**, 1072 (2004).
- ²⁸S. G. Lee, *Chem. Commun.* **2006**, 1049.
- ²⁹H. P. Steinrück, *Surf. Sci.* **604**, 481 (2010).
- ³⁰K. R. J. Lovelock, I. J. Villar-Garcia, F. Maier, H. P. Steinrück, and P. Licence, *Chem. Rev.* **110**, 5158 (2010).
- ³¹H. P. Steinrück, *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.* **14**, 5010 (2012).
- ³²W. F. Egelhoff, "Core level binding energy shifts at surfaces and in solids," *Surf. Sci. Rep.* **6**(6-8), 253 (1987).
- ³³D. P. Woodruff and T. A. Delchar, *Modern Techniques of Surface Science, Cambridge Solid State Science Series* (University Press, Cambridge, 1986).
- ³⁴W. Schattke and M. A. Van Hove, *Solid-State Photoemission and Related Methods: Theory and Experiment* (Wiley-VCH, Weinheim, 2003).
- ³⁵S. Hüfner, *Photoelectron Spectroscopy: Principles and Applications, Advanced texts in physics*, 3rd ed. (Springer, Berlin, 2003).
- ³⁶C. S. Fadley, *Surf. Interface Anal.* **40**, 1579 (2008).
- ³⁷J. F. Moulder, W. F. Stickle, P. E. Sobol, K. D. Bomben, J. Chastain, and R. C. King, Jr., *Handbook of X-ray Photoelectron Spectroscopy: A Reference Book of Standard Spectra for Identification and Interpretation of XPS Data*, Physical Electronics Incorporation (Physical Electronics, Eden Prairie, Minn., 1995).
- ³⁸D. Briggs and J. T. Grant, *Surface Analysis by Auger and X-ray Photoelectron Spectroscopy* (IM Publications, Chichester, 2003).
- ³⁹R. Streber, C. Papp, M. P. A. Lorenz, A. Bayer, R. Denecke, and H. P. Steinrück, *Angew. Chem., Int. Ed.* **48**, 9743 (2009).
- ⁴⁰A. Baraldi, G. Comelli, S. Lizzit, M. Kiskinova, and G. Paolucci, *Surf. Sci. Rep.* **49**, 169 (2003).
- ⁴¹R. Denecke, *Appl. Phys. A* **80**, 977 (2005).

- ⁴²C. Papp and H. P. Steinrück, *Surf. Sci. Rep.* **68**, 446 (2013).
- ⁴³M. Salmeron and R. Schlögl, *Surf. Sci. Rep.* **63**, 169 (2008).
- ⁴⁴H. Bluhm, M. Havecker, A. Knop-Gericke, M. Kiskinova, R. Schlögl, and M. Salmeron, *MRS Bull.* **32**, 1022 (2007).
- ⁴⁵J. Pantförder, S. Pöllmann, J. F. Zhu, D. Borgmann, R. Denecke, and H. P. Steinrück, *Rev. Sci. Instrum.* **76**, 014102 (2005).
- ⁴⁶S. Kaya, H. Ogasawara, L. A. Naslund, J. O. Forsell, H. S. Casalongue, D. J. Miller, and A. Nilsson, *Catal. Today* **205**, 101 (2013).
- ⁴⁷I. Niedermaier, C. Kolbeck, N. Taccardi, P. S. Schulz, J. Li, T. Drewello, P. Wasserscheid, H. P. Steinrück, and F. Maier, *ChemPhysChem* **13**, 1725 (2012).
- ⁴⁸E. F. Smith, I. J. Villar Garcia, D. Briggs, and P. Licence, *Chem. Commun.* **2005**, 5633.
- ⁴⁹F. Maier, J. M. Gottfried, J. Rossa, D. Gerhard, P. S. Schulz, W. Schwieger, P. Wasserscheid, and H. P. Steinrück, *Angew. Chem., Int. Ed.* **45**, 7778 (2006).
- ⁵⁰J. M. Gottfried, F. Maier, J. Rossa, D. Gerhard, P. S. Schulz, P. Wasserscheid, and H. P. Steinrück, *Z. Phys. Chem.* **220**, 1439 (2006).
- ⁵¹S. Caporali, U. Bardi, and A. Lavacchi, *J. Electron. Spectrosc.* **151**, 4 (2006).
- ⁵²O. Höfft, S. Bahr, M. Himmerlich, S. Krischok, J. A. Schaefer, and V. Kempter, *Langmuir* **22**, 7120 (2006).
- ⁵³S. Krischok, R. Otting, W. J. D. Beenken, M. Himmerlich, P. Lorenz, O. Höfft, S. Bahr, V. Kempter, and J. A. Schaefer, *Z. Phys. Chem.* **220**, 1407 (2006).
- ⁵⁴A. Riisager, R. Fehrmann, M. Haumann, and P. Wasserscheid, *Eur. J. Inorg. Chem.* **2006**, 695.
- ⁵⁵U. Kernchen, B. Etzold, W. Korth, and A. Jess, *Chem. Eng. Technol.* **30**, 985 (2007).
- ⁵⁶H. P. Steinrück *et al.*, *Adv. Mater.* **23**, 2571 (2011).
- ⁵⁷H. P. Steinrück and P. Wasserscheid, *Catal. Lett.* **145**, 380 (2015).
- ⁵⁸J. Arras, E. Paki, C. Roth, J. Radnik, M. Lucas, and P. Claus, *J. Phys. Chem. C* **114**, 10520 (2010).
- ⁵⁹M. Mezger, B. M. Ocko, H. Reichert, and M. Deutsch, *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U. S. A.* **110**, 3733 (2013).
- ⁶⁰I. Niedermaier, C. Kolbeck, H. P. Steinrück, and F. Maier, *Rev. Sci. Instrum.* **87**, 045105 (2016).
- ⁶¹E. F. Smith, F. J. M. Rutten, I. J. Villar-Garcia, D. Briggs, and P. Licence, *Langmuir* **22**, 9386 (2006).
- ⁶²S. Mehl, A. Toghan, T. Bauer, O. Brummel, N. Taccardi, P. Wasserscheid, and J. Libuda, *Langmuir* **31**, 12126 (2015).
- ⁶³M. Reichelt, T. Hammer, and H. Morgner, *Surf. Sci.* **605**, 1402 (2011).
- ⁶⁴K. R. J. Lovelock, E. F. Smith, A. Deyko, I. J. Villar-Garcia, P. Licence, and R. G. Jones, *Chem. Commun.* **2007**, 4866.
- ⁶⁵E. Elfassy, Y. Mastai, D. Pontoni, and M. Deutsch, *Langmuir* **32**, 3164 (2016).
- ⁶⁶F. L. Qiu, A. W. Taylor, S. Men, I. J. Villar-Garcia, and P. Licence, *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.* **12**, 1982 (2010).
- ⁶⁷R. Atkin, N. Borisenko, M. Druschler, S. Z. El Abedin, F. Endres, R. Hayes, B. Huber, and B. Roling, *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.* **13**, 6849 (2011).
- ⁶⁸S. Baldelli, *J. Phys. Chem. B* **107**, 6148 (2003).
- ⁶⁹N. Borisenko, S. Z. El Abedin, and F. Endres, *ChemPhysChem* **13**, 1736 (2012).
- ⁷⁰M. Druschler, N. Borisenko, J. Wallauer, C. Winter, B. Huber, F. Endres, and B. Roling, *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.* **14**, 5090 (2012).
- ⁷¹K. Motobayashi, K. Minami, N. Nishi, T. Sakka, and M. Osawa, *J. Phys. Chem. Lett.* **4**, 3110 (2013).
- ⁷²R. Wen, B. Rahn, and O. M. Magnussen, *Angew. Chem., Int. Ed.* **54**, 6062 (2015).
- ⁷³S. Bubel, S. Meyer, and M. L. Chabiny, *IEEE Trans. Electron Devices* **61**, 1561 (2014).
- ⁷⁴A. Dees *et al.*, *Inorg. Chem.* **54**, 6862 (2015).
- ⁷⁵A. Kauling, G. Ebeling, J. Morais, A. Padua, T. Grehl, H. H. Brongersma, and J. Dupont, *Langmuir* **29**, 14301 (2013).
- ⁷⁶C. C. Nguyen, S. W. Woo, and S. W. Song, *J. Phys. Chem. C* **116**, 14764 (2012).
- ⁷⁷J. P. Tafur, J. Abad, E. Roman, and A. J. F. Romero, *Electrochem. Commun.* **60**, 190 (2015).
- ⁷⁸M. T. Camci, P. Aydogan, B. Ulgut, C. Kocabas, and S. Suzer, *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.* **18**, 28434 (2016).
- ⁷⁹H. W. Cheng, P. Stock, B. Moeremans, T. Baimpos, X. Banquy, F. U. Renner, and M. Valtiner, *Adv. Mater. Interfaces* **2**, 1500159 (2015).
- ⁸⁰A. Foelske-Schmitz, D. Weingarh, A. Wokaun, and R. Kötz, *ECS Electrochem. Lett.* **2**, H13 (2013).
- ⁸¹J. Kruusma, A. Tonisoo, R. Parna, E. Nommiste, I. Tallo, T. Romann, and E. Lust, *Electrochim. Acta* **206**, 419 (2016).
- ⁸²T. Romann, O. Oll, P. Pikma, H. Tamme, and E. Lust, *Electrochim. Acta* **125**, 183 (2014).
- ⁸³A. W. Taylor, F. L. Qiu, I. J. Villar-Garcia, and P. Licence, *Chem. Commun.* **2009**, 5817.
- ⁸⁴D. Weingarh, A. Foelske-Schmitz, A. Wokaun, and R. Kötz, *Electrochem. Commun.* **13**, 619 (2011).
- ⁸⁵A. Foelske-Schmitz, D. Weingarh, H. Kaiser, and R. Kötz, *Electrochem. Commun.* **12**, 1453 (2010).
- ⁸⁶A. Foelske-Schmitz, D. Weingarh, and R. Kötz, *Electrochim. Acta* **56**, 10321 (2011).
- ⁸⁷C. A. Berger, M. Arkhipova, G. Maas, and T. Jacob, *Nanoscale* **8**, 13997 (2016).
- ⁸⁸B. Bozzini, B. Busson, A. Gayral, C. Humbert, C. Mele, C. Six, and A. Tadjeddine, *Molecules* **17**, 7722 (2012).
- ⁸⁹B. Bozzini, B. Busson, C. Humbert, C. Mele, and A. Tadjeddine, *Electrochim. Acta* **218**, 208 (2016).
- ⁹⁰R. Wibowo, L. Aldous, R. M. J. Jacobs, N. S. A. Manan, and R. G. Compton, *Chem. Phys. Lett.* **517**, 103 (2011).
- ⁹¹R. Wibowo, L. Aldous, R. M. J. Jacobs, N. S. A. Manan, and R. G. Compton, *Chem. Phys. Lett.* **509**, 72 (2011).
- ⁹²T. Cremer, L. Wibmer, S. K. Calderon, A. Deyko, F. Maier, and H. P. Steinrück, *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.* **14**, 5153 (2012).
- ⁹³F. Buchner, M. Bozorgchenani, B. Uhl, H. Farkhondeh, J. Bansmann, and R. J. Behm, *J. Phys. Chem. C* **119**, 16649 (2015).
- ⁹⁴S. Kawada, S. Watanabe, Y. Kondo, R. Tsuboi, and S. Sasaki, *Tribol. Lett.* **54**, 309 (2014).
- ⁹⁵A. Keppler, M. Himmerlich, T. Ikari, M. Marschewski, E. Pachomow, O. Höfft, W. Maus-Friedrichs, F. Endres, and S. Krischok, *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.* **13**, 1174 (2011).
- ⁹⁶M. Olschewski, R. Gustus, M. Marschewski, O. Höfft, and F. Endres, *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.* **16**, 25969 (2014).
- ⁹⁷S. Schernich *et al.*, *J. Phys. Chem. Lett.* **4**, 30 (2013).
- ⁹⁸S. Schernich *et al.*, *ChemPhysChem* **14**, 3673 (2013).
- ⁹⁹M. Sobota *et al.*, *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.* **12**, 10610 (2010).
- ¹⁰⁰K. L. Syres and R. G. Jones, *Langmuir* **31**, 9799 (2015).
- ¹⁰¹B. Uhl, F. Buchner, S. Gabler, M. Bozorgchenani, and R. J. Behm, *Chem. Commun.* **50**, 8601 (2014).
- ¹⁰²B. Uhl, M. Hekmatfar, F. Buchner, and R. J. Behm, *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.* **18**, 6618 (2016).
- ¹⁰³P. Roy, R. Lynch, and P. Schmuki, *Electrochem. Commun.* **11**, 1567 (2009).
- ¹⁰⁴I. Niedermaier *et al.*, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **136**, 436 (2014).
- ¹⁰⁵I. Niedermaier, N. Taccardi, P. Wasserscheid, F. Maier, and H. P. Steinrück, *Angew. Chem., Int. Ed.* **52**, 8904 (2013).
- ¹⁰⁶C. Kolbeck, I. Niedermaier, N. Taccardi, P. S. Schulz, F. Maier, P. Wasserscheid, and H. P. Steinrück, *Angew. Chem., Int. Ed.* **51**, 2610 (2012).
- ¹⁰⁷T. Matsuda, N. Taccardi, J. Schwegler, P. Wasserscheid, H. P. Steinrück, and F. Maier, *ChemPhysChem* **16**, 1873 (2015).
- ¹⁰⁸B. May, M. Hönle, B. Heller, F. Greco, R. Bhuin, H.-P. Steinrück, and F. Maier, *J. Phys. Chem. Lett.* **8**, 1137 (2017).
- ¹⁰⁹C. Kolbeck, N. Taccardi, N. Paape, P. S. Schulz, P. Wasserscheid, H. P. Steinrück, and F. Maier, *J. Mol. Liq.* **192**, 103 (2014).
- ¹¹⁰G. T. Rochelle, *Science* **325**, 1652 (2009).
- ¹¹¹M. Hasib-ur-Rahman, M. Siyaj, and F. Larachi, *Chem. Eng. Process.* **49**, 313 (2010).
- ¹¹²J. H. Huang and T. Ruther, *Aust. J. Chem.* **62**, 298 (2009).
- ¹¹³M. Ramdin, T. W. de Loos, and T. J. H. Vlugt, *Ind. Eng. Chem. Res.* **51**, 8149 (2012).
- ¹¹⁴B. E. Gurkan, J. C. de la Fuente, E. M. Mindrup, L. E. Ficke, B. F. Goodrich, E. A. Price, W. F. Schneider, and J. F. Brennecke, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **132**, 2116 (2010).
- ¹¹⁵E. D. Bates, R. D. Mayton, I. Ntai, and J. H. Davis, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **124**, 926 (2002).
- ¹¹⁶F. Maier, T. Cremer, C. Kolbeck, K. R. J. Lovelock, N. Paape, P. S. Schulz, P. Wasserscheid, and H. P. Steinrück, *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.* **12**, 1905 (2010).
- ¹¹⁷C. Kolbeck, I. Niedermaier, A. Deyko, K. R. J. Lovelock, N. Taccardi, W. Wei, P. Wasserscheid, F. Maier, and H. P. Steinrück, *Chem. - Eur. J.* **20**, 3954 (2014).
- ¹¹⁸T. Cremer *et al.*, *Chem. - Eur. J.* **16**, 9018 (2010).
- ¹¹⁹P. Licence, *Angew. Chem., Int. Ed.* **51**, 4789 (2012).
- ¹²⁰N. Paape, W. Wei, A. Bosmann, C. Kolbeck, F. Maier, H. P. Steinrück, P. Wasserscheid, and P. S. Schulz, *Chem. Commun.* **2008**, 3867.

- ¹²¹N. Brückner, K. Obesser, A. Bosmann, D. Teichmann, W. Arlt, J. Dungs, and P. Wasserscheid, *ChemSusChem* **7**, 229 (2014).
- ¹²²C. Papp, P. Wasserscheid, J. Libuda, and H.-P. Steinrück, *Chem. Rec.* **14**, 879 (2014).
- ¹²³S. Walter, M. Haumann, P. Wasserscheid, H. Hahn, and R. Franke, *AIChE J.* **61**, 893 (2015).
- ¹²⁴C. J. Carrasco, F. Montilla, L. Bobadilla, S. Ivanova, J. A. Odriozola, and A. Galindo, *Catal. Today* **255**, 102 (2015).
- ¹²⁵L. B. Malihan, G. M. Nisola, N. Mittal, S.-P. Lee, J. G. Seo, H. Kim, and W.-J. Chung, *RSC Adv.* **6**, 33901 (2016).
- ¹²⁶T. Peppel, M. Köckerling, M. Geppert-Rybczyńska, R. V. Ralys, J. K. Lehmann, S. P. Verevkin, and A. Heintz, *Angew. Chem., Int. Ed.* **49**, 7116 (2010).
- ¹²⁷S. J. Osborne, S. Wellens, C. Ward, S. Felton, R. M. Bowman, K. Binnemans, M. Swadzba-Kwasny, H. Q. N. Gunaratne, and P. Nockemann, *Dalton Trans.* **44**, 11286 (2015).
- ¹²⁸A. W. Taylor and P. Licence, *ChemPhysChem* **13**, 1917 (2012).
- ¹²⁹L. S. Longo, E. F. Smith, and P. Licence, *ACS Sustainable Chem. Eng.* **4**, 5953 (2016).
- ¹³⁰R. K. Blundell, A. E. Delorme, E. F. Smith, and P. Licence, *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.* **18**, 6122 (2016).
- ¹³¹H. T. Liu, Y. Liu, and J. H. Li, *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.* **12**, 1685 (2010).
- ¹³²D. Weingarth, I. Czekaj, Z. F. Fei, A. Foelske-Schmitz, P. J. Dyson, A. Wokaun, and R. Kötz, *J. Electrochem. Soc.* **159**, H611 (2012).
- ¹³³K. Fukui, Y. Yokota, and A. Imanishi, *Chem. Rec.* **14**, 964 (2014).